

Report on the Environmental Science Research Project Module (UFP) titled:

Marine Protected Time

An investigation into Time in a Marine Protected Area in
Southwest Portugal

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Oldenburg, 15th of October 2025

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Figure 1: Map showing the location and extent of PNSACV. No-take MPAs correspond to the PT and PPI zones (Source: Castro et al. (2021)).6

List of Abbreviations

ABMT	Area Based Management Tool
BBNJ	Agreement under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biological Diversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction
EU	European Union
GBF	Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
MARSW	Mar Sudoeste Project
MPA	Marine Protected Area
POPSNACV	Management plan for PNSACV
PNSACV	Parque Natural do Sudoeste Alentejano e Costa Vicentina
PPI	Partial Protection Level I
PPII	Partial Protection Level II
PT	Total Protection Level
SCI	Site of Community Importance
SPA	Special Protection Area
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea

A Time to Begin (Introduction)

Human interventions in ocean use have a long history, yet over the past 30 years, the oceans have changed more profoundly than ever before in human history (Probyn, 2020; Steinberg, 1999; Wells et al., 2016). These transformations are so extensive that effective ocean management is increasingly challenged, as some habitats are shifting into forms previously unseen by humans (Bellwood et al., 2019). Contemporary ocean management, however, happens *somewhere* - it focuses on space, such as marine protected areas (MPAs) and other area based-management tools (Peters, 2020). Yet, this is important to note, it also happens at some *time*. While time is frequently integrated into conservation targets, it often functions merely as a background frame rather than a central consideration – for example the ‘30 by 30’ target by the *Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework* (GBF) (CBD, n.d.). Moreover, the prevailing approach to *time* in ocean management is largely structured through a ‘western’ linear temporality that carries a universalist epistemological claim (Hunfeld, 2022), while there are many other aspects of *time*, or *temporalities*, to be considered.

This study then examines how *time* and *temporalities* are (only partially) considered in the establishment and management of protected spaces, particularly MPAs. *Time* in relation to protected areas is generally not well understood, highlighting a critical need to explore how *time* and people relate to the ocean and its governance (Dacks et al., 2025). Focusing on *Parque Nacional do Sudoeste Alentejano e Costa Vicentina* (PNSACV), a conservation area along Portugal’s continental coast, this research approaches the topic through three temporal lenses. The section *Linear Time* analyzes the establishment and management of PNSACV through a linear temporal lens. The following section *Temporalities beyond temporal jurisdiction* examines two non-linear temporalities - ‘slow’ and ‘fast’ - and the rhythms present in PNSACV and how these are addressed in the management of recreational and small-scale fishers. Ultimately, this study argues that planners and policymakers should account for all relevant *temporalities* in the establishment of MPAs and other spatial management tools to enhance both stakeholder acceptance and conservation effectiveness.

Methodology and research questions

This work advances a new line of inquiry by foregrounding *time* instead of space as an analytical lens, rather than treating it as the passive framework within which MPAs are conceived. This involves a reading of primary literature on PNSACV and secondary literature on *time*, MPAs and PNSACV from across the natural and social sciences. These documents¹ are analyzed qualitatively through a temporal lens and informed by broader theoretical and empirical literature². An inductive coding process was employed to identify emerging themes and to connect insights across the different literatures (Peters, 2017).

¹ Ordinances, Decree Regulations, Ministerial Resolutions and Decree-Laws translated from Portuguese into English with the help of ChatGPT (OPENAI, 2025) and DeepL (DeepL, 2025).

² See the following section *Literature Review* for more details.

The *Results and Discussion* chapter is structured around the following research questions:

1. How can the establishment of PNSACV illustrate the uses and limitations of *linear time* in the establishment and management of MPAs in general?
2. How do PNSACV regulations on small-scale fishing interact with intergenerational temporalities?
3. In what ways do human actions, including regulatory actions and local resistance, shape the experience of *time* within PNSACV?
4. Which rhythms and cycles are considered in the management of PNSACV?

The subsequent chapter engages with relevant literature from diverse fields to contextualize these research questions within the specific setting of PNSACV.

A Time to Review (Literature Review)

Marine Protected Areas as spatial tools

In 1999 the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) defined a marine protected area (MPA) as:

"any area of intertidal or subtidal terrain, together with its overlying water and associated flora, fauna, historical and cultural features, which has been reserved by law or other effective means to protect part or all of the enclosed environment" (Kelleher, 1999, p. xviii).

The primary objective of MPAs is the conservation of nature or biodiversity (Day et al., 2019; Wells et al., 2016). The 2023 *Agreement under the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biological Diversity of Areas beyond National Jurisdiction* (BBNJ) added though that the sustainable use in these areas may be allowed, provided it is consistent with the conservation objectives to their definition of MPAs³, albeit without a definition of how they should be practically managed (BBNJ, 2023; Wells et al., 2016). So, MPAs can have a wide range of different objectives (besides the primary) and therefore varying uses, depending on the context of the MPA and the country which designates and implements them. Moreover, other agencies have slightly different definitions of MPAs. There is, as such, a lot of flexibility in interpretation, when it comes to their establishment and management. Globally, MPAs vary widely - named identically across countries but differing in their protection status (Kelleher, 1999; Wells et al., 2016). So, the term 'Marine Protected Area' comes with an ambiguity which is almost tangible, were it not for its liquid nature.

Human intervention to manage ocean space is not "a recent addition to the conservation 'tool box'" (Wells et al., 2016, p. 103), but has a long history, especially when marine life was a key food source in these areas (Campbell, 2021; Wells et al., 2016). There are many examples of managed areas before the 'western' concept of protected areas emerged⁴. In many cases these concepts have become the basis of modern protected area laws, although their origins are rarely acknowledged (Wells et al., 2016). Since the mid-1800s, protected areas have evolved from terrestrial beginnings to encompass marine environments - from early marine parks and post-World War II conservation initiatives to global agreements like the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS), the Aichi Targets⁵, and the GBF's current '30 by 30' goal⁶ (Steinberg, 1999; Wells et al., 2016).

³ This flexibility has also prompted political debate regarding the potential implications of economic activities within MPAs (see Bennett et al. (2021) and Martínez-Vázquez et al. (2021) for further discussion).

⁴ In the Pacific, for instance, there are the indigenous concepts of *tapus*, *taboos*, *bul* and *ra'ui*, all of which inhibited the exploitation of resources in an area of land or sea for a defined period of time. These interventions were taken to allow stocks to recover, when resources became scarce or for spiritual or cultural reasons, among others. (Wells et al., 2016).

⁵ The international community fell short in this goal (itself controversial and scholarship raises issues with target-based goals which may lead to the creation of paper parks rather than meaningful conservation efforts. (Wells et al., 2016).

⁶ For a more details on the individual conferences and summits which have led to calls for countries to create their own national MPA systems or networks and the establishment of MPAs in areas beyond national jurisdiction (ABNJ), please see Wells et al. (2016).

What becomes obvious in the discussion of MPAs is their spatial emphasis (Lambach, 2020; Peters, 2020). The discourse is dominated by spatial terminology - "areas of total protection", "any area of land...", "area-based management tools" (ABMTs) - and debates over scale: whether large MPAs or networks of smaller ones are more effective (Leenhardt et al., 2013; Wells et al., 2016). While notions of long-term protection are frequently invoked, the temporal dimension of MPAs remains largely unexamined. How do we understand MPAs *in time*? What rhythms or *temporalities* can be found in MPAs? To address these questions, the following section introduces key perspectives on *time*, *temporality*, and rhythms.

Thinking with time

'Western' societies typically understand *time* as a linear succession of events that inexorably unfold - essentially, as the "container in which social and physical change occurs" (Peters, 2017, p. 33; Hunfeld, 2022). Accordingly, they are governed by *clock time*, which Adam (1995) describes as *universal*, *decontextualized*, and *quantitative* and to which Levine (1997) adds that *clock time* is "fixed, linear and measurable" (Levine, 1997, p. 92). In other words, in 'western' societies time is measured by a clock and thus associated with the pressure of appointments, the 'being-out-of-time', aging and everyday routines, where *time* passes no matter what. And the answer to the question, what is time, seems superfluous and seemingly in no need of an answer to manage everyday life or to be 'on time' for schedules and appointments (Adam, 1995).

This understanding of *time* is helpful under certain circumstances, although *time* should also be considered as a social construct. This relates to the social context in which time is determined - or constructed - by our knowledge of it. And this "knowledge [...] is always relative to its social setting and the outcome of an active process of fabrication" (Johnston et al., 2000, p. 748). This includes the social attitudes towards time (e.g. norms and social pressures of punctuality), different social times (*nature time*, *event time*, *clock time*), and an extended understanding of the experiences of time ('slowness' and "'fastness' or the pace of time). Moreover, rhythms can be a particular temporal manifestation of time, "which bestow a temporal sense of place" (Edensor, 2010, p. 4) through cyclical patterns of day and night, and annual or seasonal cycles of growth and decay, for instance, although these natural rhythms and cycles can be disrupted by human behavior and practices⁷ (Edensor, 2010; Edensor et al., 2020).

In the context of MPAs, *temporality* must be a key consideration. Edensor et al. (2020) describe *temporality* as the "social and cultural conceptions and perceptions of time" (p. 255), emphasizing that time is dynamic, multiple and heterogenous. In other words, *time* is not always linear; it can overlap, accelerate, or decelerate, and cannot be understood as a single universal entity. Alas, to understand *time* in cultural, spatial and social contexts there is a need to recognize the different *temporalities* that are present. Moreover, while exploring *time*, it is crucial to think not only about the everyday human

⁷ See section Rhythms and Cycles for further discussion.

temporalities, but also the non-human temporalities (e.g. landscape shifting due to tidal cycles), which may be - compared to human temporalities - slower or faster than human rhythms.

Nonetheless, it is important to understand this multiplicity of time - it can be experienced as (too) slow or (too) fast, as linear or simultaneous among other forms - as socially organized ('someone' decided to not allow fishing on Wednesday's⁸, for instance). Which means there are "embedded norms, habits and conventions" (Edensor et al., 2020, p. 255) which are responsible for governing the "when, how often, how long, in what order and at what speed" (Adam, 1995, p. 66) of everyday, weekly and annual rhythms, but also life cycles and life stage conventions (Edensor et al., 2020; Probyn, 2020).

The preceding sections have established a conceptual foundation for understanding MPAs in relation to *time*. Following a brief description of the MPA in the next section, this work explores PNSACV through multiple temporal lenses and dives into temporal characteristics that may provide a useful framework for exploring temporal dynamics of MPAs more broadly.

PNSACV

Parque Nacional do Sudoeste Alentejano e Costa Vicentina (PNSACV) is a Natural Park ("Parque Natural") located in continental Portugal. It extends roughly 130 km along the southwest coast, from São Torpes in the north to Burgau in the south, encompassing both the terrestrial area and a 2 km-wide marine strip with its adjacent seabed (see Figure 1). It was established in 1988 as a Protected Landscape Area ("Área de Paisagem Protegida") to "protect natural, cultural and other values, and also for the sustainable use of resources and habitats" (Castro & Cruz, 2009, p. 4; Decreto-Lei 241/88, 1988). In 1995 it was reclassified as a Natural Park⁹ and in 2011 several areas with different types of protection were created in the Marine Park of PNSACV¹⁰. Today it covers a marine area of 260 km² and is one of the 168 protected sites under the *Natura 2000* network in Portugal (Castro & Cruz, 2009; Castro et al., 2021; Horta e Costa et al., 2018; Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 11-B/2011, 2011). As such, PNSACV demonstrates the complex spatialities of marine protection, of overlapping designations and zones of protection within wider areas of conservation, amounting to a challenge in ocean protection (Vadrot, 2020).

⁸ For further discussion of *No-Fishing Wednesday*, see section *Time in Marine Governance*.

⁹ This reclassification enables the adoption of measures at a national level instead of a local or regional level. See the section on linear time for more detail.

¹⁰ See section Linear Time for further details on these measures and classifications.

Figure 1: Map showing the location and extent of PNSACV. No-take MPAs correspond to the PT and PPI zones (Source: Castro et al. (2021))

The coast of continental Portugal has a rich tradition in fishing and seafood harvesting due to its abundant fisheries in an eastern boundary upwelling system (Castro et al., 2021; Kämpf & Chapman, 2016). Consequently, fishing remains economically significant in southwest Portugal, while small-scale and recreational fishing also play a crucial role in socialization and supplementing family incomes (Castro & Cruz, 2009; Encarnação & Seixas, 2015; Pita & Gaspar, 2020). Many activities in the area might be framed as belonging to the Blue Economy where sustainable resource extraction is thought to be combined with conservation measures like MPAs (Jeffery et al., 2022). However, while unregulated (over)fishing - predominantly from industrial fishing - continues to negatively impact global fishery stocks¹¹ (Temple et al., 2022), PNSACV has introduced a range of regulations aimed at mitigating the negative impacts of fishing. These regulations address general fishing practices, such as permitted gear, and include site-specific measures like seasonal closures for two fish species¹² (Běláčková, 2019; Castro et al., 2021; Portaria 115-A/2011, 2011). In 2011, with the implementation of the management plan for PNSACV (POPSNACV), three different protection levels were introduced to PNSACV, total protection (PT), partial protection (PP, subdivided into type I and type II) and a complementary protection zone or buffer zone¹³ (Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 11-B/2011, 2011). See Figure 1 for a map of the areas with varying protection levels.

The monitoring and assessment of marine biodiversity and fishing impacts in PNSACV are well established, primarily through initiatives such as the Mar Sudoeste (MARSW) project (Batista et al., 2011; Castro & Cruz, 2009; Castro et al., 2021; Dias et al., 2020). Several studies have also examined stakeholder perceptions of management within the park (Castro & Cruz, 2009; Encarnação & Seixas, 2015). However, little is known about how temporal dimensions – such as *linear time*, rhythms, and *temporality* - manifest in PNSACV. This work then considers how the spatial underpinnings of MPAs has created a spatial dominance in their analysis. What might it mean to think of MPAs through different understandings of *time*, and *temporality*? How might it help us analyze their establishment and management, and to examine if and how they work effectively? This work hence addresses Marine Protected Time.

¹¹ Please see Satizábal et al. (2025) further discussions on the complexities of Illegal, unreported and unregulated (IUU) fishing.

¹² For instance, fishing for *Diplodus sargus* and *Diplodus vulgaris* is prohibited between February 1 and March 15, while the same restriction applies to *Labrus bergylta* from March 1 to May 31 (Běláčková, 2019).

¹³ In PT areas commercial and recreational fishing as well as any human presence without authorization is strictly forbidden. PPI areas are essentially 'no-take reserves', where commercial and recreational fishing is forbidden except for the commercial harvesting of barnacles on coastal cliffs. PPII areas have the function, among others, to buffer impacts on areas with a higher level of protection (PPI and PT), where fishing and sea food harvesting is allowed under certain conditions.

A Time to Discuss (Results and Discussion)

Linear Time

In this work, *linear time* refers to the ‘natural succession’ of events governed by *clock time*, as described by Adam (1995). To better understand the processes underlying the establishment and management of MPAs more broadly, this study examines the development and regulatory evolution of PNSACV through a *linear time* lens - using a timeline to illustrate both the uses and limitations of linear time in MPA governance.

In July of 1988 the *Southwest Alentejo and Vicentina Coast Protected Landscape Area* was created with a marine area of 28 858 ha to protect the natural aspects of the coastal area of Southwest Portugal and the natural, landscape, and cultural values that lie within¹⁴ (Decreto-Lei 241/88, 1988). The Protected Landscape Area was then reclassified as a Natural Park ("Parque Natural") in 1995¹⁵. This enabled the implementation of conservation measures at the national rather than local or regional level, thus integrating it into Portugal’s national network of protected areas. In the same year, the land management plan for PNSACV (POPSNACV) was approved (Decreto Regulamentar 26/95, de 21 de Setembro, 1995; Decreto Regulamentar 33/95, de 11 de Dezembro, 1995). Subsequently, PNSACV was designated as a Site of Community Importance (SCI) in 1997 and a Special Protection Area (SPA) in 1999 under the European Union’s (EU) Habitats and Birds Directives, integrating it into the Natura 2000 Network. The boundaries of these protected areas were later expanded in 2019 and 2015, respectively (*MARSW*, n.d.).

In 2006, Ordinance 868/2006 introduced national regulations governing fishing gear, bait, boat registration, catch size, and licensing in Portugal, which also applied to PNSACV. Three years later, Ordinance 143/2009 specifically addressed recreational fishing within PNSACV, introducing several iterations of what this work refers to as *No-Fishing Wednesday*¹⁶ (Portaria 143/2009, 2009; Portaria 868/2006, 2006). Sixteen years after its approval, POPSNACV was reviewed in 2011, introducing the first conservation measures for the marine area of PNSACV. and the first management and planning measures for the marine area of PNSACV were introduced. This Resolution implements the three protection levels PT, PPI and PPII (N. Castro et al., 2021; Resolução do Conselho de Ministros 11-B/2011, 2011). The final point on this timeline is the integration of PNSACV into the MPA network of the *Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic* (OSPAR) in 2015 (*MARSW*, n.d.).

So, this timeline suggests a ‘natural succession’ of events in the establishment of (networks of) MPAs, implying that aspects of *clock time* – *universal* and *decontextualized* - can be applied to these processes.

¹⁴ Certain activities within Protected Landscape Area needed the approval of its director, including the discharging of harmful wastewater, the extraction of inert materials or any minerals from the seabed and fishing, although registered artisanal fishing vessels were exempt from the director’s approval.

¹⁵ And thus, creating the acronym PNSACV.

¹⁶ The section *Time in Marine Governance* discusses this short lived, yet peculiar set of regulations for PNSACV.

However, it seems self-evident that the succession of events which led to the status quo of PNSACV are not *universal*, in the sense that it is applicable to every country's process of establishing (networks of) MPAs. There is no inherent certainty that the establishment of protected areas will progress linearly - from an initial designation to eventual integration into broader networks, as seen with PNSACV. Although such processes have been replicated elsewhere, each unfolds within its own specific context. This demonstrates that the second aspect - *decontextualized* - is also inapplicable. The implementation of these measures required specific conditions, and the regulations governing PNSACV are embedded within broader international and EU frameworks, namely the OSPAR and Natura 2000 networks.

So, returning to the uses and limitations of *linear time* in MPA governance. *Linear time* can be illustrated through a timeline of decisions, which is necessarily constructed in hindsight. As a historical tool, it allows us to visualize a succession of decisions which are borne in their time and in their place, with an outcome which can only be observed at a later point in time (and place). Different governments could have implemented alternative strategies, leading to different outcomes. When this is kept in mind, a linear perspective on time is useful for reviewing past decisions to inform future projects, even when outcomes may differ from those previously observed. *Linear time* also provides the “clarity required for the application of law” (White, 2017, p. 768) and enables precise definitions, creating an internal sense of ‘natural succession’ in regulations. For instance, European law must be transposed into national legislation within a set timeframe, as occurred in PNSACV with the designation of SCI and SPA shortly after Portugal joined the European Economic Community.

In conclusion, when *linear time* is considered within a specific context for a particular purpose and recognized for its social construction and its colonial tendencies, it serves as a valuable tool for accomplishing specific tasks, such as setting the short-term goals for an MPA at hand (Hunfeld, 2022; White, 2017).

Temporalities beyond temporal jurisdiction

Linear time can be useful management tool, although other *temporalities* are crucial in establishing and governing MPAs. As the dominant ‘western’ temporality, *linear time* carries colonial assumptions and overlooks the temporal disruptions of the Anthropocene, where natural processes are compressed and accelerated, revealing the immense scale of human impact despite limited understanding of marine ecologies (Hunfeld, 2022; Probyn, 2020).

Inspired by Probyn (2020), three *temporalities* are particularly relevant when considering MPAs. The ‘fast’ temporalities generate immediate impact on humans, such as the pace of the amendment of certain regulations through the protest against *No-Fishing Wednesday* (Encarnação & Seixas, 2015). ‘Everyday’ temporalities encompass routine practices that, while often normalized, cumulatively impact environmental outcomes. For example, stormwater runoff carrying pollutants into the sea, where “human activity reworks the spatiality of time, as our waste creates unseen and unknown but nevertheless real consequences” (Probyn, 2020, p. 182). Finally, the long-term, intergenerational or

‘slow’ temporalities, where human actions in the present will "haunt the very deep future" (Probyn, 2020, p. 182). In the case of PNSACV, this includes the potential erosion of small-scale fishing traditions and the loss of livelihoods and cultural heritage within local communities (Hunfeld, 2022; Pita & Gaspar, 2020).

These three *temporalities* are by no means exhaustive and should not be viewed as strictly separate, while also encompassing processes with cyclical temporalities or rhythms. The boundaries between the *temporalities* - like all boundaries - are fuzzy, permeable, and interwoven (Jones, 2009; Probyn, 2020). This stands in stark contrast to *linear time* described in the section above, where *time* is separated into ‘the past’, ‘the present’ and ‘the future’ and is not considered to be relational and simultaneous (Probyn, 2020). For the remainder of this chapter, the focus shifts to alternative temporalities in the management and establishment of MPAs. Specifically, it examines the ‘slow’ and ‘fast’ temporalities and the rhythms present in PNSACV, exploring the insights they offer for broader MPA governance.

Intergenerational Temporalities and Small-Scale Fishing in PNSACV

This section focuses on the ‘slow’ or intergenerational aspect of time. How do PNSACV regulations on traditional small-scale fishing interact with intergenerational temporalities? To respond to this question this work draws inspiration from Hunfeld (2022), where the intergenerational encounter lies in what ‘western’ societies call ‘the present’ and connects the generations situated before and after the contemporary generation through a temporal coexistence. In other words, the generations before and after are not in a “temporally distant or remote sphere conventionally called ‘the past’” (Hunfeld, 2022, p. 112) or ‘the future’, but rather give the individual generation the opportunity to learn, make aware and appreciate “the transgenerational sources of past, present, and future modes of being and their transmitted experiences” (p. 112).

How, then, do intergenerational encounters apply to traditional small-scale fishing in PNSACV?

Marine organisms constitute a central component of the traditional Portuguese diet, making fisheries not only an important food source but also a key site of social interaction. Fishing further supplements the incomes of low-income families, thereby sustaining the livelihoods of many coastal communities (Castro & Cruz, 2009; Castro et al., 2021; Encarnação & Seixas, 2015). In the northern part of PNSACV small-scale fishers account for approximately 73% of all registered vessels (Pita & Gaspar, 2020). Since Portugal’s overall catch has declined by half since 1980, new national regulations have been introduced in response, without the consultation and consideration of small-scale fishers (Castro et al., 2021; Diogo et al., 2020). Consequently, small-scale fishers perceive their exclusion from conservation planning as a threat to their long-term survival, due to multiple pressures such as rising operational costs¹⁷, decreasing revenues, and the resulting “lack of generational renovation” (Pita & Gaspar, 2020, p. 300).

¹⁷ Pita and Gaspar (2020) list several challenges to small-scale fishing related to low revenue from fishing in Portugal overall, including “poor management and lack of control and enforcement, lack of participation of the fishing industry in the management of their activity, lack of empowerment, increased restrictions to the fishing activity, high operational costs over the last few years [longer distances and greater depths] [and an] overexploitation of resources” (p.300). In addition to low

This demonstrates that the failure to consider traditional fishing practices in the establishment and management of MPAs risks not only the erosion of these practices but also the livelihoods of the local communities that depend on them. From a temporal perspective, such exclusion entails not only the loss of livelihood in the ‘present’ generation, but also a loss of the memory of generations before and the experiences which generations after may never have. In other words, there is a loss of the “modes of being and their transmitted experiences” (Hunfeld, 2022, p. 112).

Shifting from intergenerational temporalities, the following section examines different characters of *time* when recreational fishers experienced during *No-Fishing Wednesday*.

Time in Marine Governance

This section discusses the character of *time* itself and how it can sometimes be perceived as ‘fast’ and in other times as ‘slow’, ‘sluggish’ or not passing at all. This section focuses on the period of *No-Fishing Wednesday* and how characters of *time* were perceived during this period. In other words, how do human actions shape the experience of *time* within PNSACV?

To fully understand *No-Fishing Wednesday* it is necessary to return to a linear temporality for a moment. Ordinance (“Portaria”) 143/2009, which introduced *No-Fishing Wednesday*, came into effect in 2009 and prohibited recreational fishing from Monday to Wednesday, except on public holidays, among other regulations (Encarnação & Seixas, 2015; Portaria 143/2009, 2009). This was followed by protests from recreational fishers shortly after the Ordinance came into effect, which subsequently led to the amendment of said Ordinance through the Ordinance 458-A/2009 in May of 2009, just 3 months later. This Ordinance then prohibited recreational fishing only on Wednesdays and public holidays, thus creating the second and longest lasting iteration of *No-fishing Wednesday* (Encarnação & Seixas, 2015; Portaria 458-A/2009, 2009). In 2011, the *No-fishing Wednesday* regulation was amended to permit fishing on Wednesdays if it was a public holiday, among other amendments (Portaria 115-A/2011, 2011). *No-fishing Wednesday* was repealed in 2014, and recreational fishing was again allowed on all days of the week (Portaria 14/2014, 2014).

These regulations reveal two *temporalities*. First, they illustrate how ‘fast’ Ordinances can be amended, when urgent pressure arises and people organize protest quickly, accelerating governance in contrast to its typically ‘sluggish’ pace (Barbehön, 2022). Second, building on Barbehön’s (2022) argument that governance actively constructs its own experience of *time*, this work contends that while regulations are in effect, they can be perceived as having always been in effect and as enduring indefinitely in the perception of those affected. In other words, with the introduction of *No-Fishing Wednesday*, recreational fishers can neither ‘go back in time’ to fish on Wednesdays before the regulation came into effect, nor can they ‘skip ahead in time’ after the regulations were repealed. In this sense and regarding fishing on Wednesdays, recreational fishers are removed from the usual flow of *time* - without a ‘past’

revenue, winter weather and sea conditions make fishing more difficult, while low market prices - driven by competition with imported seafood and aquaculture - make it increasingly difficult for small-scale fishers to sustain their livelihoods. (Pita & Gaspar, 2020).

or a ‘future’ – and experience *No-Fishing Wednesday* entirely in the present. In essence, prohibiting recreational fishing on a Wednesday (or any other day by that matter) without the ‘silver lining’ of being able to fish again on that day - e.g. through seasonal closures or similar measures - creates a stark ‘on-off’ situation, where *time* becomes ‘slow’, ‘sluggish’ or even halts. This leaves recreational fishers ‘lost in stagnation’, while industrial (over)fishing and other oceanic cycles around them continue, or even accelerate¹⁸, and keep moving in *time*.

Having discussed two different aspects of *time*, the following section turns to how (natural) rhythms and cycles influence fishing and management practices.

Rhythms and Cycles

Water movement operates through interconnected cycles that span vastly different temporal scales. These range from relatively rapid processes, such as the evaporation of sea water and its return as precipitation within days to weeks or the millennia-long journey of water masses through thermohaline circulation. Here, for example, water can sink in the Labrador Sea and resurface in upwelling zones along the Portuguese coast (Kämpf & Chapman, 2016). Life in coastal communities, then, adheres to additional cycles and rhythms. Daily tides come and go in a regular six hour rhythm, the migration of various life forms due to seasonal changes and the effect these seasonal changes have on fishing practices due to different weather conditions in summer and winter (Castro et al., 2021). Furthermore, carbon is exchanged cyclically between the ocean, the atmosphere and life forms through the so-called Carbon Cycle¹⁹. All of these cycles and rhythms can affect the primary and secondary production of the ocean in coastal ecosystems, as well as limit fishing activities and the consequences of these limitations, such as longer soak time of nets, which lead to more discards (Castro et al., 2021; Kämpf & Chapman, 2016). And these cycles and rhythms are reliable²⁰, where what is inserted into the ocean returns at some time again - be this waste or Carbon - due to its rhythmic and cyclical nature (Probyn, 2020).

So, rhythms and cycles frame the processes of the ocean and the life it sustains, both within and beyond it. Which of these rhythms and cycles are considered in the management of PNSACV?

Fishing catches in PNSACV are constrained by seasonal factors, with catches generally lower in winter than in the summer months (Castro et al., 2021). Returning to *No-Fishing Wednesday*, the authors of Ordinance 458-A/2009 recognized when considering seasonality that "the limitation of recreational fishing to four days a week did not sufficiently consider the frequently adverse sea conditions specific to the area, which alone constitute a limiting factor for recreational fishing" (Portaria 458-A/2009, 2009, p. 1) and thus limited recreational fishing to Wednesdays only.

¹⁸ See Probyn (2020) for examples of acceleration in natural cycles, especially their concept of compressed time.

¹⁹ The oceanic carbon cycle, shaped by biogeochemical and physical processes, is driven mainly by the solubility and biological pumps, which transfer carbon between surface and deep waters (Kämpf & Chapman, 2016).

²⁰ Although some of these rhythms and cycles can be accelerated due to the emission of carbon into the atmosphere. For instance, melting ice caps release stored carbon, driving ocean acidification at rates unseen in 50 million years. (Smithsonian Institution, 2014).

Rhythms and cycles can be found in conservation measures in PNSACV, where popular measures among fishers include annual closed seasons for different species of fish and a suggested “rotation of fisheries closure in space and time” (Castro & Cruz, 2009, p. 387; Běláčková, 2019). These regulations align with natural cycles, such as seasonal changes or the life cycles of particular species. Likewise, fishing activity follows comparable rhythms: according to Castro and Cruz (2009), recreational fishing and shellfish collecting on the rocky shores in PNSACV is more intensive at certain points of a daily or annual cycle - specifically, during the summer, at low tide and on the weekend and public holidays.

So, natural rhythms and life cycles are generally considered in the regulation of commercial and recreational fishing in PNSACV. Spatio-temporal measures, such as temporal closures for specific species in designated areas demonstrate how seasonality is also taken into account (Běláčková, 2019). These regulations adhere to (local) natural rhythms and cycles and while relying on spatial understandings of conservation measures, there is a partial consideration of *time* in the management of PNSACV, albeit the linear cyclical succession of a calendar, or *linear time*. Studies on fishing and conservation measures in PNSACV (e.g. Castro & Cruz, 2009; Encarnação & Seixas, 2015) call for the co-management of local users, which - if implemented - could incorporate multiple *temporalities* beyond *linear time*.

In summary, the temporal dimensions observed in PNSACV demonstrate that *time* extends beyond a linear framework. Transgenerational knowledge transmission, recreational fishers’ perceptions of *time* during *No-Fishing Wednesday* and the reliable patterns of the rhythms and cycles in PNSACV reveal a complex interplay between the multiple *temporalities* that shape both the ecological systems and a coastal way of life. This marks how important it is for planners to consider non-linear time (and its importance for the local users) in the establishment and management of an MPA.

With the conclusion of this section on different *temporalities* in PNSACV, this work then broadens the local manifestations of *time* into a more general discussion on why and how to incorporate *time* into the planning and management of MPAs.

A Time to conclude (Conclusion)

As the previous sections have shown, *time* is multifaceted. It can progress one second at a time along a timeline, but also interweave, where the separation of past, present and future is non-existent. It can be experienced as simultaneous, but also one can be forced out of *time* itself. Reliable rhythms shape oceanic and coastal life, yet some cycles are accelerated and thereby compressing deep time (Hunfeld, 2022; Probyn, 2020).

So, the challenges moving forward lie in developing management approaches that recognize and integrate these multiple *temporalities* and ensure that regulatory measures work with the marine ecosystems and the communities that depend on them. In other words, when *time* is solely understood as this linear and inexorable entity and other *temporalities* are omitted in the establishment and governance of MPAs, then there is the risk of overlooking *temporalities* that are crucial in the acceptance and conservation success of any individual MPA or marine governance in general, for that matter. As the *linear time* section has shown, timelines can be used as a planning tool for implementation steps that depend on preceding actions, where planners need clear definitions and thus adhere to a calendar or *clock time*. But environmental governance should respond to ecological temporalities and not a calendar. It should focus on the detailed knowledge of local users and their relationships with the sea, which varies depending on where and when you are in a seascape (McKinley et al., 2024). Furthermore, when relying on *linear time* while planning MPAs, one “define[s] problems as they are understood by western science and policy makers” (Peters, 2020, p. 14) and thus risks reterritorialization, or in other words, neocolonial modes of governing any marine environment (Hunfeld, 2022; Peters, 2020). An example for this is the concern of small-scale fishers operating in MPAs in Portugal, that their practices are not considered in the management of the MPA (Pita & Gaspar, 2020). So, in the same way that there is no ‘one-size-fits-all’ where an MPA is, there is no ‘one-time-fits-all’ to when an MPA is.

A Time to continue

However, Castro and Cruz (2009) suggest temporal management and co-management steps when considering future regulations in PNSACV. They should involve “co-management approach[es] that should allow co-responsibility of users and managers in an adaptive and integrated process” (p. 4) by creating a network of MPAs, where local users are involved in selection and management. Additionally, a redrawing of the boundaries of the MPA networks after “some years” (p. 4), to adapt to the experiences made by the networks.

Beyond these management suggestions, further research, with additional methodology, is needed to understand how *time* and *temporalities* relate to MPAs. How does the compression of time affect PNSACV specifically? How does time relate to non-coastal MPAs, like large-scale or High Seas MPAs? Do other modes of management, such as dynamic conservation methods, include nonlinear temporalities? This list is not complete, as the relations between *time* and (marine) protected areas remain understudied.

So, while there is a real risk to revert to (neo)colonial and exclusivist modes of governance when planners adhere to *linear time*, it is important to “move reflections on time to the centre of their considerations” (Hunfeld, 2022, p. 100; Antonello, 2019). This means to foster an understanding that protecting the ocean means protecting the diverse rhythms and temporalities of life and livelihood that make coastal communities resilient across generations.

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